

Infrared spectra of charge transfer complexes of bis(N-H-salicylaldiminato)Cu^{II}

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Abstract : The infrared spectra of new charge transfer complexes based on bis(N-H-salicylaldiminato)Cu^{II} have been studied. The donor chelate interacts with the standard acceptors like TCNQ, DDQ, chloranil, TCNE, TNF and iodine through charge transfer binding interaction. It is found that all charge transfer complexes are Peierls semiconductors except TCNE complex. TCNE complex is a Mott or Hubbard semiconductor. The spectra of all the complexes are mainly governed by donor spectrum and not by acceptor spectra as in the purely organic radical-ion salts. TCNE, DDQ and TNF complexes have well developed absorption compared to chloranil, TCNQ and iodine complexes in 1800–3000 cm⁻¹ region. Three absorption envelopes are found in some cases in the infrared range as in the case of strongly correlated electron systems.

Keywords : Charge transfer complexes, organic acceptors, infrared spectra, optical conductivity, band assignments.

Only limited work has been reported on charge transfer complexes of organometallic chelates with purely organic donors and acceptors¹. Some of these complexes are found to have appreciable electrical conductivity². It is interesting to study whether major charge transfer interactions arise from the metal ions or from the organic network. There are few charge transfer complexes of organometallic chelates, which have metal chain in one direction^{3–5}. The lead phthalocyanine and metal chain dioximes are studied by one of the authors⁴. Now we come to a third group, i.e. salicylaldiminates of nickel and copper, which have metal chains⁶ and some of which have been found to be antiferromagnetic.

Among the recently studied metal complexes poly (1,1'-ferrocenylene) doped with TCNE is an example which was highly conducting⁷, near IR photoconductivity and the number of ferrocenylene units in oligo and poly dihexylferrocenylene show positive correlation⁸. Magnetic susceptibility and EPR studies have also been reported⁹. Spin anisotropy play dominant role in spin dynamics of low-dimensional copper systems¹⁰. Double bridged linear chain copper dipyrindine dibromide and copper dipyrindine dichloride have been studied and the line widths are interpreted with anisotropic exchange theories¹¹. Self-assembled monolayers of nickel(II) Schiff base has also been studied¹². Metal complexes are more suitable for molecular electronics and optoelectronic materials¹³. Optical transmission study of the films of copper phthalocyanine along with pentadecyl TCNQ was studied¹⁴. Cobalt complexes with Schiff base obtained by condensation of aniline with salicylaldehyde cobalt (II) com-

plex was studied¹⁵. Both metal-connected ligand and ligand-connected metals systems are found to be important in molecular electronics¹⁶. Zn(RNAFIN)₂ TCNQ were synthesized and electronic delocalization was concluded¹⁷. Metal-organic chromophores are found to be non-linear optical materials¹⁸.

The Little's original model of excitonic mechanism¹⁹ was revised for organometallic systems²⁰. Macrocyclic ligands like porphyrins and chlorophylls show Soret band and excitons²¹. Phthalocyanine is also a π -conjugated ligand like porphyrin. There are synthetic problems in Little's model. The chelating agent loses reactivity once it reacts with a metal ion, i.e. metal chelates are non-reactive. But metal chelate can work either as an electron donor or as electron acceptor and form charge transfer complexes with purely organic acceptor or a donor. This is tried in the present study. There is a possibility of high temperature superconductivity in such compounds, which are one-dimensional conductors, due to exciton mechanism. Therefore, we study such compounds.

Experimental

Bis(N-H-salicylaldiminato)Cu^{II} was prepared by a reaction of salicylaldehyde, ammonia solution and CuCl₂·6H₂O in the presence of a base (KOH). The chelate was formed through an exothermic reaction. The traces of Cu(OH)₂ were removed from the precipitates by washing with concentrated KOH solution and then the precipitates were filtered and naturally dried for 3–4 days. The donor chelate was grinded in a mortar to form a fine powder. The donor chelate was mixed with each of the acceptors like 7,7,8,8,-tetracyano-*p*-

Table 1a. Optical and infrared properties of CT complexes of Cu(N-H-salim)₂

Name of the complex	Colour	Absorption function	Nature of transition	Value of E_g (eV)
Cu(N-H-salim) ₂ -TCNQ	Greenish blue	$\alpha = \alpha_0 (h\nu - E_g)^3$	Forbidden indirect	0.2125
Cu(N-H-salim) ₂ -TCNE	Black	$\alpha = \alpha_0 (h\nu - E_g)^3$	Forbidden indirect	0.2775
Cu(N-H-salim) ₂ -TNF	Greenish yellow	$\alpha = \alpha_0 (h\nu - E_g)^3$	Forbidden indirect	0.225
Cu(N-H-salim) ₂ -DDQ	Black	$\alpha = \alpha_0 (h\nu - E_g)^2$	Allowed indirect	0.225
Cu(N-H-salim) ₂ -chloranil	Brown	$\alpha = \alpha_0 (h\nu - E_g)^{1/2}$	Allowed direct	0.2313
Cu(N-H-salim) ₂ -I ₂	Dark brown	$\alpha h\nu = \alpha_0 (h\nu - E_g)^2$	Allowed indirect	0.2125

quinodimethane (TCNQ), tetracyanoethylene (TCNE), 2,4,5,7-tetranitro-9-fluorenone (TNF), 2,3-dichloro-5,6-dicyano-*p*-benzoquinone (DDQ), 2,3,5,6-tetrachloro-*p*-benzoquinone (chloranil) and iodine. Each mixture was crushed and grinded in a mortar with a pestle for about 15 min till a change in colour was observed. The original bis(N-H-salicylaldiminato)Cu^{II} chelate is green coloured. It forms different colours in different acceptors as mentioned (Table 1a). The molecular structures of the donor chelate and acceptors are shown in Fig. 1.

The samples for infrared spectroscopic measurements were prepared in the form of microcrystalline pellets by grinding the each charge transfer complex after mixing with dry KBr powder and then compressing it in a die. The Fourier Transform Infrared Spectra (FTIR) in the range 400–4000 cm⁻¹ were recorded on single beam GRDX FTIR spectrophotometer made by Perkin-Elmer Co. USA having a resolution 0.15 cm⁻¹ scan range 15600–30 cm⁻¹, scan time 20 scan/s, OPD velocity 0.20 cm/s and MIRTGS and FIRTGS detectors were used.

Results and discussion

The infrared spectrum of bis(N-H-salicylaldiminato)Cu^{II} is shown in Fig. 2. There is featureless absorption at wave

numbers above 1700 cm⁻¹. This cannot be assigned to any absorption between valence band and conduction band as recently assigned in only Tmbine²². This is because the band gap along the copper chains lies in UV-visible-near IR range and not in the infrared range. The dipole moment of a two-fold symmetric chelate is not large. The metal chain is responsible for the absorption, which shows that it is a microcrystalline sample. The region below 1700 cm⁻¹ is a finger printing region (means a unique feature of the specimen) and the band assignments²³ have been carried out (Table 2a). There are two broad envelopes below 1700 cm⁻¹, one around 1300 cm⁻¹ and the other around 750 cm⁻¹. This shows the possibility of two electrons vibrating across the ligand. There is electron-intramolecular vibration coupling. The in-phase oscillations occur in UV-visible range and the out of phase oscillations occur in the infrared range.

The fine structures are resonance shapes as found from damped-driven oscillator function. The overall envelope profile seems to be a beta density around 1300 cm⁻¹ and Lorentzian around 750 cm⁻¹. The spectrum should be compared with those of metal dioximes, which reveal one-electron problem. When a charge transfer complex of the donor chelate is formed, the resonance line shapes are either sharpened or broadened with either a red shift or a blue shift de-

Table 1b. Details of absorption envelopes

	High frequency envelope			Low frequency envelope		
	Intensity (A)	K_{max} (cm ⁻¹)	Full width at half-maximum	Intensity (A)	K_{max} (cm ⁻¹)	Full width at half-maximum
Cu(N-H-salim) ₂ -TCNQ	50	1700	950 (G)	50	755	350 (G)
Cu(N-H-salim) ₂ -TCNE	85	1625	310 (L)	70	754	100 (L)
Cu(N-H-salim) ₂ -TNF	83	1300	950 (G)	75	754	500 (G)
Cu(N-H-salim) ₂ -DDQ	100	1450	700 (G)	95	755	450 (G)
Cu(N-H-salim) ₂ -chloranil	92	1350	650 (G)	80	754	450 (G)
Cu(N-H-salim) ₂ -I ₂	30	1617	100 (L)	15	754	200 (L)

G means Gaussian and L means Lorentzian.

Table 1c. In σ_{\max} vs n

Name of the complex	Transmission minimum (T) (%)	Absorbance arb. units (%)	$\sigma = \alpha n_1 C/4\pi \cdot 10^{10} \text{ (s}^{-1}\text{)}$	In σ_{\max}	No. of bands in the (n) envelope
Cu(N-H-salim) ₂ -TCNQ	50	50	1.19	23.20	10
Cu(N-H-salim) ₂ -TCNE	12	88	2.10	23.77	13
Cu(N-H-salim) ₂ -TNF	20	80	1.91	23.67	12
Cu(N-H-salim) ₂ -DDQ	0	100	2.39	23.90	15
Cu(N-H-salim) ₂ -chloranil	10	90	2.15	23.79	13
Cu(N-H-salim) ₂ -I ₂	70	30	0.72	22.7	8

pending on whether softening of lattice vibrations occur or anharmonic effects become important. The spectra are not mere superpositions of donor and acceptor spectra but do change upon the formation of the charge transfer complexes. The complete band assignment of each charge transfer complex was carried out and presented in Tables 2b and 2c. The absorption by the acceptor becomes prominent above 1700 cm^{-1} . It is observed that the red-shifted bands are sharpened and blue-shifted bands are broadened. Double envelope below 1700 cm^{-1} become more pronounced in all the charge transfer complexes. TCNQ and TCNE complexes show asymmetric envelopes while TNF complex shows symmetric envelope. The envelopes around 1700 cm^{-1} and 750 cm^{-1} are asymmetric Gaussian bands in TCNQ complex. In TCNE complex, the envelope around 750 cm^{-1} has a Lorentzian shape. The TNF complex shows symmetric Gaussian bands around 1700 cm^{-1} and 750 cm^{-1} . DDQ and chloranil complexes show broad background absorption in which there are no transmission dips and resonance-anti-resonance spikes.

Table 2a. Band assignments in the spectrum of bis(N-H-salicylaldiminato)Cu^{II}

Wavemumber	Band assignment
1643	$\delta_{\text{N-H}}$
1535	$\nu_{\text{C=N}}$
1434	$\delta_{\text{C-H}}$
1353	$\nu_{\text{C-O}}$
1240	$\nu_{\text{C-C}}$
1146	$\nu_{\text{C-N}}$
1100	$\nu_{\text{C-C ring}}$
1060	$\nu_{\text{C-C ring}}$
1040	$\nu_{\text{C-C ring}}$
1000	$\nu_{\text{C-C ring}}$
940	$\nu_{\text{C-O}}$
897	$\pi_{\text{C-H}}$
823	$\pi_{\text{C-H}}$
756	$\pi_{\text{C-H rocking}}$
675	$\pi_{\text{C-H}}$
615	Group vibration
500	Metal-ligand (M-L)
494	M-L

Fig. 1. Molecular structures of the donor chelate and organic acceptors.

There are three methods of plotting the envelopes, viz. (i) an overall envelope by joining the transmission dips, (ii) an envelope passing through the mid-points at half-maxima of all bands and (iii) an envelope joined through transmission peaks (or a background absorption)²⁴. The band gap defined by $\alpha = 0$ or maximum transmission is found 0.22 eV around 1700 cm^{-1} in all the complexes except the TCNE complex. In TCNE complex, it is 0.275 eV around 2200 cm^{-1} . It implies that TCNE is one-electron Mott or Hubbard semiconductor while others are Peierls semiconductors. In chloranil complex, monotonically changing absorption is not found above 1700 cm^{-1} but a broad peak gives 0.26 eV energy around 2100 cm^{-1} . From this it is confirmed that the chloranil complex is a photoconductor. Photoconductivity is a famous phenomenon²⁵.

There is a dispersion shape in TCNQ complex while it is a resonance shape in DDQ and TCNE complexes at 2221

Table 2b. Band assignments in the IR spectra of CT complexes of Cu(N-H-salim)₂

Cu(N-H-salim) ₂ -TCNQ		Cu(N-H-salim) ₂ -TCNE		Cu(N-H-salim) ₂ -TNF	
Wave number (cm ⁻¹)	Band assignment	Wave number (cm ⁻¹)	Band assignment	Wave number (cm ⁻¹)	Band assignment
3312	ν_{N-H}	3312	ν_{N-H}	3311	ν_{N-H}
3050	ν_{C-H}	2203	$\nu_{C=N}$	3087	ν_{C-H}
2222	$\nu_{C=N}$ (TCNQ)	1625	δ_{N-H}	1740	ν_{C-O}
1532	δ_{N-H}	1531	$\nu_{C=C}$	1623	δ_{N-H}
1444	δ_{C-H} (sym)	1445	δ_{C-H} (sym)	1538	ν_{NO_2}
1340	ν_{C-C} (unsym)	1343	δ_{C-H} (unsym)	1445	δ_{C-H}
1222	ν_{C-C}	1274	δ_{C-H}	1346	δ_{N-H}
1200	ν_{C-N}	1226	ν_{C-C}	1300	δ_{NO_2}
1145	ν_{C-O} (sym)	1184	ν_{C-N}	1223	ν_{C-C}
1116	ν_{C-O} (unsym)	1145	ν_{C-O}	1144	ν_{C-O}
1061	ν_{C-C} (ring vib)	1116	ν_{C-O}	1091	ν_{C-O}
1000	ν_{C-C} (ring vib)	1026	ν_{C-C}	922	ν_{C-NO_2}
950	ν_{C-C} (ring vib)	939	ν_{C-C}	895	ν_{C-NO_2}
920	ν_{C-C} (ring vib)	894	ν_{C-C}	819	ν_{C-C}
895	ν_{C-C} (ring vib)	819	ν_{C-C}	754	ν_{C-C}
870	ν_{C-C} (ring vib)	754	π_{C-H}	728	π_{C-H}
817	ν_{C-C} (ring vib)	668	π_{C-H}	709	π_{C-H}
755	π_{C-H}	609	π_{C-H}	668	π_{C-H}
668	π_{C-H}	553	Group vib	609	π_{C-H}
608	π_{C-H}	500	M-L	554	Group vib
554	Group vib	448	M-L	477	M-L
475	M-L			449	M-L
440	M-L				

cm⁻¹. This band which can be assigned to $\nu_{C\equiv N}$ (stretching C≡N) interact differently in TCNQ complex which is a symmetric molecule and ordinarily in DDQ and TCNE which are asymmetric or non-planar molecules. Symmetry and planarity give rise to a fine-structure in 1800–3000 cm⁻¹ range of spectra of CT complexes of TCNQ, TNF and chloranil

molecules while it is absent in DDQ and TCNE complexes which are asymmetric or non-planar. A comparison with the CT complexes of PbPc (lead phthalocyanine) and nickel dioximes⁴ shows that the spectra did not exactly contain bands of the donor chelate while in the present work on salicylaldiminate ligand, the infrared spectra of CT complexes are governed by mainly donor chelate bond vibrations. In

Table 2c. Band assignments in the IR spectra of CT complexes of Cu(N-H-salim)₂

Cu(N-H-salim) ₂ -DDQ		Cu(N-H-salim) ₂ -chloranil		Cu(N-H-salim) ₂ -iodine	
Wave number (cm ⁻¹)	Band assignment	Wave number (cm ⁻¹)	Band assignment	Wave number (cm ⁻¹)	Band assignment
3162	ν_{N-H}	3312	ν_{N-H}	3428	ν_{N-H}
2217	$\nu_{C=N}$	1691	δ_{N-H}	3310	ν_{N-H}
1623	δ_{N-H}	1625	δ_{N-H}	2925	Unknown
1445	$\nu_{C=N}$	1531	$\nu_{C=N}$	1617	δ_{N-H}
1277	ν_{C-C}	1444	$\nu_{C=N}$	1530	$\nu_{C=N}$
1145	ν_{C-C}	1341	ν_{C-O}	1442	$\nu_{C=N}$
1077	ν_{C-O}	1259	ν_{C-C}	1222	ν_{C-C}
1025	ν_{C-C}	1225	ν_{C-C}	1146	ν_{C-O}
886	ν_{C-C}	1114	ν_{C-N}	1116	ν_{C-N}
819	ν_{C-C}	1025	ν_{C-C}	1021	ν_{C-C}
756	π_{C-Cl}	894	ν_{C-C}	891	ν_{C-C}
699	π_{C-H}	819	ν_{C-C}	816	ν_{C-N}
668	ν_{C-C}	754	π_{C-H}	754	π_{C-H}
609	ν_{C-Cl}	712	π_{C-H}	667	π_{C-H}
556	M-L	669	ν_{C-Cl}	606	π_{C-H}
449	M-L	609	ν_{C-Cl}	446	M-L
		555	Group vib		
		480	M-L		
		450	M-L		

Fig. 2. Infrared spectrum of bis(N-H-salicylaldiminato)Cu^{II}.

CT complexes of PbPc and nickel dioximes, only indirect gaps are found while here both direct and indirect gaps are found depending upon donor-acceptor interactions (Fig. 3 and Table 1a). Direct gap is found in chloranil complex as an exception; all others show indirect transitions. There is a pronounced band around 3100 cm⁻¹ in DDQ and TCNE complexes and only partially developed in chloranil complex while it is absent in TCNQ and TNF complexes. This implies to be related with the interaction of asymmetric and non-planar DDQ and TCNE.

The bands at 1622 cm⁻¹ and 1445 cm⁻¹ in DDQ complex are broadened compared to these bands in other complexes. This can be related with asymmetry of DDQ molecule. The 1445 cm⁻¹ band is a triplet or quadruplet in TCNQ, TNF and chloranil complexes and is a singlet or doublet in DDQ and TCNE complexes. The band splits in an electric field of counter-ion in stronger acceptors. In this sense, DDQ and TCNE are weaker acceptors than TCNQ, TNF and chloranil. The acceptor bands are not pronounced in any CT complex because of lack of ionic nature of the present CT complexes. Only in radical-ion salts, acceptor bands govern the infrared spectra. The spectrum of only the donor chelate shows beta density around 1300 cm⁻¹ in the range 1000–1600 cm⁻¹ while

the spectra of CT complexes show asymmetric Gaussian band related with tunneling of charge density waves through a rectangular potential of donor due to the internal electric field of counter-ions. The two envelopes in each case whether Lorentzian or Gaussian shape are summarized (Table 1b).

Usually a direct transition is found in 90% of the organic complexes while in the CT complexes of metal chelate, both of the direct and indirect transitions are possible. When the interaction is weak direct transition occurs and when the charge transfer interaction is stronger, indirect transition occurs. This is confirmed in the present study. The infrared spectra are also related with the dimensionality²⁶. They are electronic in nature, since the absorption functions depend on dimensionality. In this way TCNQ and chloranil complexes are almost two-dimensional and other four complexes are one-dimensional in crystalline form and three-dimensional in an amorphous form.

High-resolution spectra revealed harmonic generation and hetero-dyning (frequency mixing) in organic charge transfer complexes. Such a thing is not possible in the present work where the donor bands are well defined. However, anharmonic vibrations can lead to blue-shift of some of the bands.

Fig. 3. Nature of transitions in the charge transfer complexes of Cu(N-H salim)₂

One or two bands may be arising from combination modes, particularly the broad harmonics. The TCNQ and TCNE complexes transmit infrared light in the range 800–1100 cm⁻¹. Other complexes also transmit in this range but transmission does not exceed 70%.

As absorption increases, reflectivity also increases and both are related through

$$R = \frac{(\eta - 1)^2 + \left(\frac{\lambda^2}{16\pi^2}\right)\alpha^2}{(\eta + 1)^2 + \left(\frac{\lambda^2}{16\pi^2}\right)\alpha^2}$$

where λ is wavelength, R is reflectivity, η is refractive index and α is the absorption coefficient²⁷. When α is small as we use only 5% CT complex in 95% KBr powder, the reflectivity is also small and can be neglected. Even if α and R both are present, the absorption spectra are governed by reflectance spectra. This can be safely assumed. A transmission dip shows both reflectance peak and absorption peak.

The samples of all the materials used in the present work are microcrystalline and not amorphous as the metal chains govern spectra above 1700 cm⁻¹. The fractal dimensionality is quasi-one or quasi-two dimensional as indicated by the absorption functions. No large band tails are found, as it

Fig. 4. Band tailing in TCNE and Redfield effect in all other charge transfer complexes

should be found for amorphous materials. Band tails are Urbach tails of the order of 0.03 eV, which is nearly thermal energy (Fig. 4). The tunneling of charge carriers from valence to conduction band when an external electric field is applied is called Franz-Keldysh effect. Such tunneling of charge carriers or charge density waves can also occur in an internal electric field of counter-ion particularly in an ionic compound. This was suggested by Redfield²⁸. For the Franz-Keldysh effect²⁹,

$$\alpha_E = \alpha_0 \exp \left[-\gamma \frac{(\omega_G - \omega)^{3/2}}{E} \right]$$

where $\gamma = \frac{4\sqrt{2}\mu\hbar}{3e}$, $\hbar\omega_G$ is the band gap and E is the electric

field. Thus $(\ln \alpha)^{2/3}$ vs $\hbar\omega$ (or $h\nu$) should be a straight line. Because of this we plot here $(\ln \alpha)^{2/3}$ vs $h\nu$ (eV) (Fig. 4). Iodine and TNF complexes show this effect. In other complexes this effect is negligible. TCNE complex only shows band tailing in which $\ln \alpha$ vs $h\nu$ is a straight line. The asymmetric Gaussian bands around 1300 cm^{-1} found in TCNQ and TCNE complexes may be due to the frequency dependence of real part of refractive index $\eta_1(\omega)$ as it appears in $\sigma(\omega) = [\alpha(\omega)\eta_1(\omega)c]/4\pi\sigma(\omega)$ can be symmetric and so the asymmetry in $\alpha(\omega)$ arises through asymmetry in $\eta_1(\omega)$, which has dispersion shape.

There is a dip in the absorption envelope in the chloranil complex, which may be related to the change in the density of states with energy. The free-carrier absorption is given by³⁰

$$\alpha_f = A\lambda^{1.5} + B\lambda^{2.5} + C\lambda^{3.5}$$

where A , B and C are constants and λ is wavelength. $\lambda^{1.5}$ term arises from scattering by acoustic phonons, $\lambda^{2.5}$ through optical phonons and $\lambda^{3.5}$ through ionized impurities. The absorption coefficient α is $100 - T$ for semiconductors and $\alpha = T$ for highly conducting materials. Here we have made an approximation that $\log \alpha$ is proportional to $-\log T$. This approximation works better than more accurate and complex computations particularly in chloranil, TCNQ and TNF complexes, where α increases (i.e. T decreases) as wavelength increases (i.e. wave number decreases). This is found in 3200–3800 cm^{-1} range in these three complexes. A direct linear plot of $\log T$ vs $\log \lambda$ gives slopes of 1.44, 1.21 and 1.44 in chloranil, TCNQ and TNF complexes respectively³¹. This shows that acoustic phonons are the dominant scatterers of charge carriers in this class of complexes and this is consistent with their neutral and non-ionic nature. The strong accepting nature of TCNQ, TNF and chloranil stabilizes conduction band and this leads to the free-carrier absorption due to phonon scattering.

The plot of $\log \sigma_{\text{max}}$ vs n , where σ_{max} is the maximum optical conductivity from maximum absorption in the envelope and n is the number of coupled vibrations indicated by number of bands in the envelope is linear (Table 1c). A band at 754 cm^{-1} gets split in 754, 727 and 709 cm^{-1} as an asymmetric at some what red-shifted wave number in TNF complex. This splitting is not found in any other complex. However, a band at 699 cm^{-1} develops in DDQ complex and 712 cm^{-1} in chloranil complex.

Conclusion :

The charge transfer complexes of bis(N–H-salicylaldiminato)Cu^{II} are found to be Peierls semiconductors except TCNE complex. The absorption functions above 1700 cm^{-1} reveal either a direct or an indirect transition. The Gaussian and Lorentzian envelopes are identified which have fine-structure of resonance line-shape because of damped-driven oscillator model. There are two electrons across the molecule of the donor chelate like phthalocyanine and porphyrins. The infrared spectrum of the chelate reveals out-of-phase oscillations of two electrons.

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